

Microencapsulation of bovine serum albumin by solvent evaporation and *in situ* polymerization techniques

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This paper presents two techniques for microencapsulation of bovine serum albumin (BSA), namely, solvent evaporation and *in situ* polymerization. Both these processes have been designed to give improved loading and release rates. We achieved high encapsulation efficiency with high microcapsule yield using high power ultrasonication for formation of microemulsion and an efficient microsyringe for the formation of double emulsion. *In situ* polymerization in the organic (methyl methacrylate, MMA) liquid membrane of the microemulsion was conducted in inert atmosphere. Both the methods are cost-effective and may be designed for predetermined release of the biomaterials.

Microencapsulation is receiving increasing attention as a means of formulating pharmaceuticals for controlled release purposes. A great number of microencapsulation techniques are available. The choice of one particular method is primarily determined by the solubility characteristics of the drug and polymer. The process of solvent evaporation has found wide-spread application for the microencapsulation of drugs in most investigations. Attention has been focused on solid matrix microspheres prepared by a single emulsion process. A method of producing reservoir-type microcapsules involving the utilization of multiple emulsion systems has been reported¹. The water/oil/water (W/O/W) technique is reported to be superior to oil/water/oil (O/W/O) emulsion system. In fact, the use of an external oil phase of the O/W/O type has many disadvantages : the agglomeration of the microcapsules, difficulty of clean-up requirements of the final product, loss of the organic phase and the high viscosity of the external phase. The knowledge and control of process variables in any process are of fundamental importance for obtaining relevant information of the process and product with reproducible technical and biopharmaceutical properties.

Polyesters such as poly(lactic acid) (PLA), poly(glycolic acid) (PGA), poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), and their copolymers have been extensively investigated as matrices for controlled delivery of many micro- and macromolecules during the past decades. Two widely employed methods are solvent evaporation and phase separation. Both make use of organic solvents, the most commonly employed solvent being dichloromethane (DCM). The PLA/PGA polymers usually have very high melting points and, therefore are not

commonly employed for encapsulating drugs and especially proteins by the polymer melting method². In this study, we have encapsulated a model protein BSA in ethyl cellulose (EC), cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB), PMMA (polymethylmethacrylate) and CPMMMA (chitosan modified polymethylmethacrylate) by solvent evaporation and *in situ* polymerization, and examined the morphology of microcapsules and release profile of the entrapped protein *in vitro*. Chitosans are linear polysaccharides with low toxicity, that are biodegradable and biocompatible. They have been considered for various biomedical and pharmaceutical applications for enhanced release³. In the area of drug delivery systems chitosans and their derivatives have been usefully employed in the preparation of drug loaded microparticles. Chitosan microspheres or microcapsules have been prepared by emulsion or multiple emulsion cross-linking, simple coacervation, complex coacervation, emulsion/solvent evaporation, and spray drying⁴.

This study attempts to overcome some of the problems associated with the % release and loading capacity by employing a process of multiple emulsion solvent evaporation and *in situ* polymerization to fabricate reservoir-type microcapsules by the very commonly available polymers, e.g. EC, PMMA, chitosan-PMMA, and cellulose acetate butyrate. These techniques are potentially advantageous for the microencapsulation of high molecular weight polypeptides because the active material can be maintained in a predominantly aqueous environment during the microencapsulation⁵ and may be subsequently released by aqueous diffusion through water/buffer filled pores formed in the polymer membrane.

Results and Discussion

Both solvent evaporation and *in situ* polymerization processes generated spherical type microcapsules as observed by SEM analysis. The most interesting features of these microcapsules are that these are stable and can be stored for months and they can retain a high core to external membrane ratio of the biomaterials. Though Fickian diffusion may be used for prediction of release of low molecular weight species from microcapsules, it is not a proper mechanism to describe release of macromolecules such as BSA. The release of proteins can be achieved by biodegradation, diffusion through aqueous pores and channels generated by previously dissolved proteins or by rupture of polymer capsules as a result of sorption of buffer by hydrophilic protein or through well defined aqueous pores created during the fabrication process⁶.

BSA release from microcapsules :

BSA release studies were conducted as described in the experimental section. Fig. 1 shows the release of BSA with time for ethyl cellulose (EC) and CAB microcapsules. It is very clear from the figure that both gave almost total release after 10 days. But the rate of release for CAB is almost linear, while for ethyl cellulose, the release was very low in initial few days and shot up rapidly over a period of two days. The results show that changing polymers give changes in the release pattern considerably and may be exploited for a predetermined release characteristics.

Fig. 2 depicts the percentage release of BSA with time for the PMMA and chitosan modified PMMA microcapsules. The significant result is that neat PMMA could give low release and it became almost insignificant after 4 days whereas a chitosan modified PMMA gave much better re-

Fig. 1. *In vitro* release of BSA from ethylcellulose (EC) and cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB) microcapsules prepared by multiple emulsion solvent evaporation method.

Fig. 2. *In vitro* release of BSA from poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and chitosan-PMMA microcapsules made by emulsion polymerization.

lease (up to 76%) over a span of 8 days. This supports our hypothesis that BSA release might depend on the sorption of water by the hydrophilic part (chitosan). It is obvious that by varying the amount of chitosan we may change the release characteristics.

The loading efficiency was found to be 92% for chitosan-PMMA, and 91% for CAB.

We have been successful in establishing two processes of making microspheres using very commonly available monomer and polymers giving very high values of loading efficiency.

Experimental

Reagents of analytical grade and double-distilled water were used throughout. Bovine serum albumin (Sigma), cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB) (National Chemicals, India), polystyrene (MW 325000–350000), poly(vinyl alcohol) (MW 125 000), dichloromethane (DCM) (E. Merck), Tween 80 and Span 85 (Sigma) were used as received.

Preparation of microcapsules :

Solvent evaporation technique using CAB and ethyl cellulose (EC) : (a) CAB : A modified method over the two-step emulsification procedure⁴ was adopted. In the first emulsification step, double-distilled water (2 ml) containing BSA (5 mg) was emulsified in the polymer solution (10%, w/v, of cellulose acetate butyrate in dichloromethane). This was emulsified in a sonicator (Sonics and Materials Inc., USA, VCX 600) with span-85 (200 μ l) to make w/o emulsion. The above emulsion was added slowly to an external aqueous (15 ml) phase having 0.5%(w/v) poly(vinyl alcohol) and Tween 80 (300 μ l) to yield a w/o/w multiple emulsion. The multiple emulsion was stirred on magnetic stirrer to drive away DCM. The microcapsules thus obtained

were separated in a centrifuge (Hettich Universal 32) at 8000 rpm for 30 min, then washed with water and allowed to dry at 4° for 24 h.

(b) *EC* : BSA (5 mg) was dissolved in water (2 ml) and ethyl cellulose (0.3 g) was dissolved in DCM (8 ml) separately. Microemulsion and multiple emulsion was made as described above and the microcapsules obtained were stored at 4°.

In situ polymerisation technique with MMA and chitosan-MMA :

In this case solution (5 ml) of BSA (30 mg) in water was added to methyl methacrylate (5 ml) and span-85 (500 μ l) and the mixture was emulsified as above. The emulsion was then sprayed in a reaction vessel containing distilled water (25 ml) and initiator ($K_2S_2O_8$). Nitrogen gas was purged through the reaction mixture for 10 min. The mixture was kept at constant temperature of 50° for 3 h and then transferred into large amount of stirred water. The powdered product that separated by centrifuge was washed, dried and kept at 4°.

For making chitosan-PMMA microcapsules, 2% chitosan solution (5 ml) was also added to the aqueous BSA solution in the above procedure.

Scanning electron microscopy was conducted using a JEOL electron microscope operating at 10 kV. The magnification power on the screen ranged from 100 to 3500.

BSA release studies :

In vitro release of BSA from microspheres was carried out in the following manner. BSA loaded microspheres (50 mg) were added to 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4; 50 ml) in reagent bottles and tumbled at room temperature. At definite time interval, aliquot (0.5 ml) was withdrawn, and the BSA content estimated by the Lowry's method, again mak-

ing background corrections due to adsorbed PVA using the control dissolution medium. Dissolution was replenished after withdrawal of each aliquot. Values plotted are average of three determinations along with standard deviation. The rate of BSA release was monitored till no appreciable release was observed.

Encapsulation efficiency and % release :

The encapsulation efficiency may be expressed as the ratio of the actual BSA content in the microcapsules to the theoretical BSA loading expressed as a percentage. This was obtained by the protein analysis in supernatant from the centrifuge plus wash buffer of the microcapsules. The loading was calculated by material balance of protein used. The % release was calculated based on BSA analysis of the dissolution phase and loading efficiency.

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